

**“More exciting than curate’s croquet” — reconstructing the origins
of South Africa’s lawn tennis tradition, 1860–1900**

Hendrik Snyders

Centre for Military Studies, South African Military Academy, Saldanha, 7395, South Africa
Research Fellow, Department of History, University of the Free State, P.O. Box 339, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa
Honorary Research Fellow, National Museum Bloemfontein, P.O. Box 266, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa
E-mail: snydersh@sun.ac.za
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8630-4122>

ABSTRACT

During 2023, South Africa marked 120 years of organised tennis on a national basis. Over this period, a number of players of both sexes achieved international fame on a number of iconic courts in a range of competitions. In the recent past, the national honours list which for more than a century only reflected the achievements of people of white and European descent, witnessed the addition of the names of a number of black achievers. This notwithstanding, the real origins of the South African lawn tennis tradition remain largely unknown and the cause of speculation. This article, using a range of contemporary historical newspaper archives, provides a new reconstruction of the origins and development of tennis within both the white and black communities in the period before the Second Anglo-Boer War (South African War).

KEYWORDS: South Africa, gender, lawn tennis, race, sport.

INTRODUCTION

In 2018, Kgothatso Montjane (born 3 June 1986), a wheelchair tennis player, became the first black South African woman to compete at Wimbledon. In the same year, she also competed at the US Open. With these two accomplishments, she became the first African wheelchair tennis player to qualify for all four Grand Slam tournaments in the same year. Montjane’s achievements, followed that of Lucas Sithole, who won the British Open wheelchair tennis tournament (Super Series) in Nottingham in July 2011, and the US Open Grand Slam in 2013. Sithole in turn, was the first African player to have won a Super Series Event or a Grand Slam.

These historical landmarks were not surprising and had their origins in the existence of a century-old tennis tradition among black South Africans, which, however, remained largely unknown to the majority of the population and the global tennis fraternity. In addition, the sacrifices and contribution of generations of tennis players, administrators and their associations, unions and Boards within the Black community has faded into obscurity, potentially never to

be unearthed. This has contributed to the continued marginalisation of the Black sporting past which denied the nation the benefit of having a full record of the efforts of its sporting heroes to be used as a tool for building social cohesion.

Ironically and contrary to expectations, the real and detailed origins of the sport amongst members of the White community equally remain the cause of speculation and guesswork. Both G.A. Parker and H.P. Swaffer, the pioneers of the first written records of the sport in South Africa, situated its introduction on the southern tip of Africa during the 1870s.¹ Given their inability to determine the exact date for the establishment of the sport in South Africa, the South African Tennis Union (SATU), the first national coordinating body since 1903, on the occasion of its 75th anniversary in 1978, with no other information at its disposal noted that “there is plenty of dispute over where tennis was first played in South Africa”.² Similarly, the same brochure, quoting the journalist Force Kashane with regard to the history of tennis amongst South Africa’s Black communities, noted that by the mid-1970s, the growth of the sport was constraint by negative perceptions such as

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- 1 See G.A. Parker, *South African Sports* (London: Sampson Low, Marston & Co., 1897), 143–44, <https://books.google.co.il/books?id=Y5oLhBilGPcC>; and H.P. Swaffer, ed., 1914, *South African Sport* (Johannesburg: Transvaal Leader, 1914), pp. 50–1. Despite an extensive search through the available contemporary newspaper archives, neither of the two authors’ Christian names could be traced. Contemporary news reports consistently referred to them in the formal manner and with reference to their initials.
- 2 Russell Eldridge, *Tennis: the South African Story: Commemorating the 75th Anniversary of the South African Tennis Union* (Johannesburg: Owen Williams, 1978), p. 10.

a sport being only fit for female. Consequently, this misconception and bias “resulted in a slow flow of people into the game”.³ These and other statements, lack a strong factual basis and are not consistent with the available information in, for example, newspaper archives.

The scholarly literature on the origins, early history, and further development of South African lawn tennis remains sparse. Stellenbosch sports historian, Francois Cleophas' recent study (2023) into the development of the tennis tradition of the Cape Colony and its embeddedness within the colonial class structure and politics, remains a notable exception and a pioneering work.⁴ However, due to its narrow geographical focus, it fails to properly account for the national spread of the sport and for becoming an integral part of South Africa's national sports identity. In addition, the article, for lack of space, failed to fully explore the emergence and subsequent development of a strong black lawn tennis tradition. As far as tennis during the apartheid era up to the unification of the sport (1948–1991) is concerned, notable contributions were made by historians Farieda Khan and Saleem Badat.

Whereas Khan's focus of investigation is the tennis struggles of black female players and their battle against gender discrimination and patriarchy, in addition to institutionalised racism, Badat's recent publication explores the first overseas tour (and its associated challenges) of a group of six male (Coloured and Indian) players in 1971.⁵ Given this scope, Badat's narrative, while foregrounding the biographies of the male tourists, chiefly concerns itself with their on-tour experiences, interactions and performances. While the book further situated the players' on- and off-court struggles within a broader fight for social justice, it, however, failed to adequately explore issues such as gender discrimination and patriarchy, as well as providing a more nuanced understanding of the intersection between ideology and ethnicity in the tour group's ethnic composition.

The skirting of complex issues such as gender bias and patriarchy is particularly surprising given Khan's call more than a decade ago (2010), for the ending of the obscurity of women's tennis history, and for reversing its “lower levels of media attention”.⁶

Given the lack of a comprehensive national sports history of Black South Africans and women, and the general absence of complete and easily accessible official archives, it is incumbent on the national sports federations, the South African Sports Confederation and Olympic Committee (SASCOC), and the national and provincial government to begin to reverse the situation and to continuously record the broader and inclusive history of South African sports such as tennis for posterity.

METHODOLOGICAL CONSIDERATIONS

“History”, noted Dave Day and Ray Vamplew, “remains a genre of empirical knowledge that is based upon the remains of the past and, unless there is some evidence from the past, there can be no sports history”.⁷ Internationally, the preservation and documentation of the historical records of most sporting codes vary between national coordinating bodies, primarily because of a lack of financial resources, the inability to appoint official full-time archivists, and a struggle to secure sufficient and appropriate storage space.⁸ Consequently, most organisations, often with little consideration for the need for complete historical records in the future, are constantly disposing of materials and records in order to optimise space. Terry Cook, with reference to the ‘weeding’ of archives, cautioned against this practice, and remarked that “we are what we keep, we keep what we are!”.⁹ Martin Johnes similarly advised that a failure to catalogue archival material, effectively means that “the information within an archive is, for all practical purposes, lost”.¹⁰

Despite the availability of a vast amount of information about the South African lawn tennis past

3 Force Kashane, “Black Tennis,” in *Tennis: the South African Story: Commemorating the 75th Anniversary of the South African Tennis Union*, R. Eldridge (Johannesburg: Owen Williams, 1978), p. 35.

4 Francois Johannes Cleophas, “In a Class of its Own? The Origins and Early History of Tennis in the 19th-Century Cape Colony,” *Journal of Southern African Studies* 49, no. 5–6 (2023), pp. 947–64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057070.2023.2324410>

5 Saleem Badat, *Tennis, Apartheid and Social Justice: The First Non-Racial International Tennis Tour, 1971* (Pietermaritzburg: UKZN Press, 2023).

6 Farieda Khan, “Anyone for Tennis? Conversations with Black Women Involved in Tennis during the Apartheid Era,” *Agenda* 85 (2010): 82 (76–84). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27917368>

7 Dave Day and Wray Vamplew, “Sports History Methodology: Old and New,” *The International Journal of the History of Sport* 32, no. 15 (2015): 1717 (1715–24). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523367.2015.1132203>

8 Tony Collins, “Sports History at the Coalface: Developing the British Rugby League Archives,” *ASSH Bulletin* 28, June (1998): 7 (7–8).

9 Terry Cook, “‘We are What We Keep; We Keep What We are’: Archival Appraisal Past, Present and Future.” *Journal of the Society of Archivists* 32, no. 2 (2011): 173–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00379816.2011.619688>

10 Martin Johnes, “Archives and Historians of Sport,” *The International Journal of the History of Sport* 32, no. 15 (2015): 1785 (1784–98). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523367.2015.1108307>

in contemporary newspapers, and, to a lesser degree, in public and private archives, the sport like so many others, is engaged in a struggle to end its “archival obscurity”.¹¹ For the purposes of this article, extensive use were made of textual sources, particularly contemporary newspaper archives housed in a variety of collections, including the National Library of South Africa and the University of the Witwatersrand Historical Archives. The latter collection also contains a significant volume of documentation (minutes of meetings, match programmes, brochures and other ephemera) from the former non-racial Tennis Association of South Africa (TASA). Although it was found useful for the identification of continuities within the Black lawn tennis tradition, most of the last-mentioned material falls outside of the scope of the current study. Material extracted from historical newspapers, was supplemented by photographs (Figs 1–5) from the special photographic collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein. This material despite its local nature was still found useful for identification of players and for giving a sense of the evolution of both equipment and dress over time. No oral histories covering the founding years of lawn tennis in South Africa were discovered, forcing the historian to reconstruct the past almost exclusively from newspapers, secondary literature, photographs and other fragmentary sources of evidence.

PIONEERING A ‘WHITE’ TENNIS TRADITION

According to some of the available newspaper archives, the earliest indicators of the tennis presence in South Africa started to appear as early as 1860. During March of that year, an advertisement in the *Eastern Province Herald* indicated that the retailer Savage & Hill based in Port Elizabeth (currently Gqeberha) announced to the public the availability of a large consignment of manufactured goods for sale, including tennis balls.¹² This suggests that there were indeed some tennis enthusiasts amongst the settled frontier population of the eastern districts of the Cape Colony. Two years later, another retailer, G. Hallack of Port Elizabeth, advertised the receipt and availability of an imported consignment of manufactured goods, which included “hollow and solid industrial rubber” cricket and rubber balls.¹³ This deliberate marketing of tennis equipment, strengthens the suspicion that

the sport was indeed beginning to demonstrate a long-term presence in parts of the Colony. By 1864, the Bloemfontein newspaper the *Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette* in its report about a hailstorm in the city, described the situation as follows:

“almost every inhabitant of the town was taken by surprise by a very sudden fall of hail. The hailstones bounded on our flat roofs like tennis balls, and everyone thought that his neighbour was taking the liberty of playing a game of “fives” on his particular house-top, and upon rushing out to stop the “little game” was saluted by “one for his nob” and compelled to retire before the shower of – stones!”¹⁴

The utilization of the tennis language suggests that the newspaper’s readers were not only acquainted with the sport, but also understood some of its key terminology. Otherwise throughout the years, a range of newspapers indicated the arrival of imported goods including items described as “novelty goods” such as lawn tennis aprons and caps, lawn tennis pouches and lawn tennis walking costumes.¹⁵ In addition, the *Cape Times* promoted tennis equipment similar to that used in the Wimbledon Tennis Championships and imported from the United Kingdom, locally.¹⁶

Against this background and given the reported absence of any organised lawn tennis clubs, it is safe to assume that the sport by the beginning of 1870 was mostly played on an individual basis. Judging by advertisements of auctions and sales in the colonial newspapers of the time, tennis courts formed an integral part of the properties of the rich and wealthy. It also became the scene for lawn tea parties, fit even for those in the priesthood and allowed all with an opportunity to experience “scenes of edification, refreshment, and amusement” while maintaining their “ecclesiastical dignity”.¹⁷ Being also relatively inexpensive, these parties in comparison to the practice at croquet parties, required the minimum refreshments.

Throughout the decade, tennis courts and equipment appeared in the inventory lists of auctioneers as part of either deceased or insolvent estates. This was often a feature of the auction lists of departing colonial officials or prominent citizens from the Cape Colony in general and Cape Town in particular. Examples in this regard included the auction of the property of ‘Wynberg Villa’ of the Late Judge James Coleman

11 Richard Fagan, “Acquisition and Appraisal of Sport Archives,” *ASSH Bulletin* 16, April (1992): 36 (36–47).

12 “Savage & Hill,” *Eastern Province Herald*, March 2, 1860, p. 1.

13 “Cricket Bats and Balls,” *Eastern Province Herald*, December 19, 1862, p. 1.

14 “Thunder and Hailstorms,” *Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*, October 21, 1864, p. 3.

15 “Mrs Stonier,” *Cape Times*, August 17, 1880, p. 1.

16 “The Grand Tennis Tournament at Wimbledon,” *Cape Times*, September 16, 1880, p. 2.

17 “Law Tennis Parties,” *Cape Times*, October 21, 1878, p. 3.

Fitzpatrick as advertised in the *Cape Times*.¹⁸ Similarly, 'Great Westerfoord' the estate of Justice Simeon Jacobs in Main Road Newlands, another Cape Town suburb, had one.¹⁹ Further the Wynberg property, "Oaklands", that belonged to a Dr Payne,²⁰ was put on the market following his departure from Cape Town and upon relocation to Bloemfontein for health reasons.²¹ Some estates, such as the auctioned goods of the departing governor of the Cape Colony, Sir Henry Bartle Frere in August 1880, also included a number of tennis items.²² Against this background, a newly arrived resident through the letter page of the *Cape Times* called for the construction of tennis courts close to railway stations to aid those with a desire to play competitively against others in different towns and districts.²³

By the start of the 1880s, lawn tennis, still being a novelty, continued to be played on an individual basis judging by the ongoing advertisements in the colonial press.²⁴ However, the first attempt to change this state of affairs was also launched at this time in Cape Town, when several local tennis players launched a public subscription in honour of Major Walter Clopton Wingfield who took the initiative to establish tennis on a formal basis in the United Kingdom. According to the *Cape Times* newspaper, Wingfield originally promoted the sport as an activity that "gave girls an athletic game which they can play in summer time in healthy open air, a game more exciting than curate's croquet, and full of charm".²⁵ Subsequently it spread worldwide and found, among others, a significant foothold in South Africa at large. This was arguably also aided by the development of the local capacity by companies such as W. Kemm of Cape Town to make "lawn and tennis fields to order with neatness".²⁶ Just before the end of 1879, a Cape Town retailer, Packham & Co. located in Adderley Street in their November advertisement notified the buying public that they, in addition to a separate club set of lawn tennis, racquets, balls and nets, also had 200 pairs of ladies and gents tennis shoes in stock.²⁷

By September 1880, the *Cape Times* reported on the existence of a new club, the Suburban Lawn Tennis Club based in the suburb of Rondebosch with H. Graham Cloete as Secretary and Treasurer.²⁸ This was, according to all evidence, the first dedicated lawn tennis club established in the city and the country. However, very little information about its first year of operations or its other executive members could be traced. The only real indication of the club being active was its public notice of the resumption of the 1880 season in the *Cape Times* in November 1880 under the hand of its Honorary Secretary George Piers, in which the club members were encouraged to also invite their friends.²⁹ Almost a year later, the local media carried an advertisement for an urgent members meeting to "determine the future of this club".³⁰ This suggest that developing the sport in the absence of other clubs to compete with was particularly challenging for the pioneers of lawn tennis in South Africa. Nevertheless, the club survived and by November 1882, it was able to call an annual general meeting to plan for the new year.³¹ At that point the local media also reported on the presence and activity of the Gardens Lawn Tennis Club.

By March 1883, the existing Cape Town clubs were joined by the Rondebosch and Claremont Lawn Tennis clubs who played each other at the former's courts.³² Others that made an entry subsequently were the Wynberg and Sea Points clubs, as well as occasional teams such as the 'Officers of the Highlanders' and 'Officers of the Garrison'. Thus, on 6 July 1883, and testifying to further positive growth, the four existing formal clubs plus the Garrison met at the Masonic Hotel in the City to form the Western Province Lawn Tennis Association (WPLTA). Claremont, although unrepresented at the meeting, was regarded as of common mind and thus regarded as a founding member. On this occasion, the assembled clubs adopted a set of ten operating rules, which inter alia made provision for play accordance to the Marylebone Rules, the launch of a Challenge

18 "Valuable Property for Sale," *Cape Times*, March 3, 1880, p. 1.

19 "Public Sale of Valuable Landed Property," *Cape Times*, April 10, 1880, p. 1.

20 A significant number of historical newspapers often failed to provide full names or initials of the individuals named in their reports.

21 "Sale of the Charming Residence "Oaklands" at Wynberg," *Cape Times*, September 23, 1880, p. 2.

22 "Sale of Horses, Carriages, Harness etc. etc.," *Cape Times*, August 14, 1880, p. 1.

23 "Correspondence," *Cape Times*, May 9, 1878, p. 3.

24 "Xmas Novelties," *Cape Mercantile Advertiser*, December, 18, 1876, p. 3.

25 "Sales and Other Announcements," *Cape Times*, July 13, 1881, p. 3.

26 "Notice," *Cape Times*, July 12, 1879, p. 4.

27 "Something New," *Cape Times*, November 29, 1879, p. 4.

28 "Suburban Lawn Tennis Club," *Cape Times*, September 1, 1880, p. 1.

29 "Suburban Lawn Tennis Club," *Cape Times*, November 2, 1880, p. 3.

30 "Suburban Lawn Tennis Club," *Cape Times*, August 24, 1881, p. 1.

31 "Rondebosch," *Cape Times*, November 1, 1882, p. 1.

32 "Local Intelligence," *Cape Times*, February 3, 1883, p. 2.

Cup Competition, institution of an annual Singles Championship, and fixing the start and the end of the regular season.³³ Thus at the end of the first Challenge Cup season played between Wynberg and Gardens in February 1884, the former walked away with the honours after defeating their more fancied opponents.³⁴ Their prize, which was imported from England, was only handed to them at a special reception in April after its arrival.³⁵

Following the conclusion of the successful WPLTA's inaugural season of organised tennis, more clubs joined over the next period. These included the South African College School, and the likes of Rouwkoop House and Belvidere.³⁶ Due to a lack of detailed information very little is known about the players involved or the frequency of their interaction. By the year end, and testifying to further growth, the WPLTA consisted of five suburban and two country clubs.³⁷ It was hoped to also include a consolidated club consisting of members of the Garrison located in Cape Town and Simon's Town.

Beyond Cape Town, in the eastern districts of the Cape Colony, lawn tennis soon also found its first footing. Several retailers such as James Brister & Co. and John M. Levick & Co. in Port Elizabeth continue to carry tennis equipment among their stock. In March 1880, the *Eastern Province Herald* noted the opening of a Railway sports club in the town of Somerset East with an adjoining grounds suitable for a variety of codes including lawn tennis.³⁸ Whether such a club was actually in existence is, however, unknown. Shortly thereafter, a Cradock resident took the initiative to convert a part of the municipal commonage in the village into a facility for tennis and croquet where "the health, youth, and beauty of the town assemble nearly every afternoon and attract an admiring following".³⁹ During 1882, a new club

was also formed in Port Elizabeth. Over the first two years of its existence, it had to rely on its own members for competition.⁴⁰ In this regard it launched an annual Gentleman's Singles Championship. This saw E.B. Pagden becoming the first "champion racquet" of the eastern districts during March 1883.⁴¹ This coincided with reports about lawn tennis activity in Humansdorp which, according to the *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, suffered under a crime spree.⁴²

By 1884, Port Elizabeth was joined by a new club in Grahamstown. This created an opportunity for the hosting of the first inter-town match between the new organisation and its neighbours from Port Elizabeth. Concomitant with these developments, retailers of women's clothing and sports equipment in diverse locations including Grahamstown also extensively advertised lawn tennis shoes and related equipment as part of their sale catalogues.⁴³ Two years later, the colonial media noted the existence of a lawn tennis club in Kimberley, a distant neighbour of the eastern districts. This created new optimism and hope that the Kimberley Lawn Tennis Club would become part of a future inter-town competition.⁴⁴ With a short period, the club was joined by the Gardens Lawn Tennis Club in the city who received prominence for initiating an annual tournament soon after its establishment.⁴⁵ In this regard in October 1892, the club hosted the Kimberley Lawn Tennis Tournament where seven titles including the Gardens Lawn Tennis Club Exhibition Trophy and the Championship of Griqualand West was at stake.⁴⁶

The formation of the Durban Lawn Tennis Club, in 1886 in the colony of Natal was preceded by the institution of the sport on the gardens of Government House by Governor Sir Garnet Wolseley during 1875⁴⁷ and by the founding of the Richmond Tennis

33 "Lawn Tennis," *Cape Times*, July 10, 1883, p. 3. The rules of lawn tennis were for the first time formally revised on 26 April 1872 by the Marylebone Cricket Club (a multi-sport social club, despite its name). It was also used for the first Wimbledon Championships in 1877. A further revision took place in 1880 and was adopted by the All-England Croquet and Lawn Tennis Club, London.

34 "Lawn Tennis," *Cape Times*, February 12, 1884, p. 3.

35 "Lawn Tennis," *Cape Times*, April 2, 1884, p. 3.

36 "Sporting Intelligence," *Cape Times*, February 11, 1886, p. 3.

37 The members included Gardens, Wynberg, Sea Point, Rondebosch, Claremont, Paarl and Mowbray. See also "Sporting Intelligence," *Cape Times*, November 25, 1886, p. 3.

38 *Eastern Province Herald*, March 9, 1880, p. 3.

39 "Local and General News," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, June 14, 1881, p. 6.

40 "Lawn Tennis Tournament," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, March 10, 1883, p. 5.

41 "Lawn Tennis Championship," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, March 22, 1883, p. 2.

42 "Weekly Notes," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, September, 18, 1883, p. 5.

43 See, for example, "Star Bank Dividend!" *Cape Times*, January 3, 1884, p. 1; "J.D. Jones & Co – Boots and Shoes," *Cape Mercantile Advertiser*, May 5, 1884, p. 2; and "Footballs, Lawn Tennis Sets, Best Regulation Club Balls," *Eastern Province Herald*, July 23, 1884, p. 6.

44 "Laws of the game," *Cape Times*, December 11, 1886, p. 3.

45 "Lawn Tennis," *Johannesburg Times*, November 7, 1895, p. 5.

46 "Lawn Tennis," *Cape Times*, October 14, 1892, p. 3.

47 "Sir Garnet Wolseley in Natal," *Natal Witness*, July 27, 1875, p. 3.

Club, the oldest in South Africa, in 1876.⁴⁸ This set a powerful example for tennis enthusiasts and others interested in promoting the sport. However, due to its exclusivity and accessibility to only those within close proximity of the governor, it soon attracted criticism from a reader of the *Natal Witness*. Writing under the assumed name of “Bohemian”, the correspondent questioned the confinement of lawn tennis to those in political circles and accused the colonial authorities of collaborating in maintaining a monopoly over the playing of the sport and promptly called for the public promotion thereof.⁴⁹ During the Anglo-Zulu War shortly thereafter, British soldiers stationed within the territory, played lawn tennis in addition to polo, quoits and engaged in boxing.⁵⁰ In so doing, they provided the sport with an important boost. Although public establishments such as hotels throughout the 1880s started to advertise tennis as one of their recreation offerings, together with others such as billiards, croquet, badminton and quoits, general access to the sport were slow in coming.⁵¹ Matters were also not helped by a certain degree of prejudice, arguably of a sexist nature, against the sport. In this regard, the Natal Football Association took a resolution prohibiting its members from mixing with the local lawn tennis fraternity/club since it would be “derogatory” and “undignified to associate”.⁵² This notwithstanding, British soldiers stationed within the territory, continue to play and providing the sport with a necessary growth spurt and foothold.

During 1882, the Berea Lawn Tennis Club was established. This was assisted by the retail activities and offering of tennis equipment for sale by the likes of local companies such as P. Davis & Sons, who offered their products in response to the rising popularity of “this fashionable game”.⁵³ Two years later, the growing community saw the founding of its second club, the Maritzburg Lawn Tennis Club. This laid the basis for the introduction of a regular inter-town competition against Durban complete with championships such as the Maritzburg and Durban Championship, as well as the Annual Natal Championship, for both men and women. In February

1884, the *Pietermaritzburg Commercial Advertiser*, noted that

“lawn tennis is becoming very popular in Durban and matches of note are not infrequent. It is undoubtedly very pretty to watch and has many claims to consideration by the youth of the place, chief amongst them being that the fair sex can partake in the enjoyment. It seems almost to be eclipsing that real old English pastime of cricket, which our fathers and grandfathers swore by, and many people believe that by and bye cricket bats and stumps will all be sold in lots for firewood owing to the successful rivalry of the racquet and net. Tennis is certainly a far more effeminate game than cricket, but the tendency of the times is all for refinement and ‘culcha,’ and I suppose games requiring prolonged exertion will have to give way to those which give opportunities for showing liveness of body and grace of attitude. There seems to be a good deal of ‘love’ about tennis, perhaps that accounts for its popularity during the present marrying and giving in marriage period.”⁵⁴

By the end of the decade, tennis players in Durban were still without appropriate facilities and were forced to use any available open space, including public for their activity.⁵⁵ By the mid-1890s following the victory of the young Churton Collins over the seasoned Arthur Butcher, the local newspaper reports noted that it gave Natal new hope for the future South African championship.⁵⁶

By the 1880s, tennis was also a reality in the Transvaal. Reports indicated that by 1881 during the First Anglo-Boer War, lawn tennis, in addition to croquet and polo, formed an integral part of the militia activities permitted during martial law.⁵⁷ Key players in this regard were the officers and members of the Garrison. Their activity, however, was not universally welcomed and was indeed on occasion criticised by members of the public as wasteful and unnecessary spending that was not in the interest of the Colony.⁵⁸ For others, however, these activities brought a sense of normality and an indicator that the city was not “yet

48 Charmian Coulson, “Beaulieu-on-Illovo: Richmond Natal: Its People and History,” (Richmond: Richmond Women's League and Institute, 1986), cit. after J.M. Nicholson, “Book Reviews and Notices,” *Natalia* 17 (1987): 106 (105-7).
<http://natalia.org.za/Natalia/no17.html>

49 “Bohemian,” *Natal Witness*, June 27, 1876, p. 2.

50 “Zulu Armistice,” *Natal Witness*, March 15, 1879, p. 5.

51 “Turner's Hotel,” *Natal Witness*, January 3, 1880, p. 2.

52 “Weekly Notes,” *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, October 31, 1882, p. 3.

53 “Lawn Tennis,” *Natal Witness*, November 29, 1879, p. 1.

54 “Local and General News,” *Pietermaritzburg Commercial Advertiser*, February 29, 1884, p. 2.

55 “Local News,” *Natal Witness*, December 21, 1880, p. 3.

56 “Tennis,” *Johannesburg Times*, May 27, 1895, p. 5.

57 “The Condition of Affairs in the Transvaal,” *Cape Times*, February 28, 1881, p. 4.

58 “The Transvaal,” *Cape Times*, June 9, 1881, p. 4.

Figure 1: Nineteenth-century Bloemfontein Tennis playing gentlemen.

a heap of ruins”.⁵⁹ The first official lawn tennis club in the Transvaal, Wanderers Lawn Tennis Club was founded during 1888. As part of its programme, and arguably also to promote itself, the new club hosted a club championship twice per week on Wednesday and Saturday. The matches on Wednesday afternoons in particular, however, proved to be a challenge as a result of diminishing daylight which was aggravated both by the trees that surrounded the Wanderers courts or the glare from the nearby ice rink.⁶⁰ Otherwise, the players had to contend with dust storms, in addition to a failure of entrants to its championships to respond timeously which prevented the clubs from publishing the events in the local media on a regular basis.⁶¹ This notwithstanding, the club championships were enthusiastically supported by both those male and female players who took the trouble to participate.

On 5 August 1891, Wanderers as the pioneer club in the Transvaal Republic, and following a significant increase in the number of active tennis clubs, together with a group of others with an interest in a

better coordinated and overarching control body met to establish the Transvaal Lawn Tennis Association (TLTA).⁶² Amongst these were clubs such as United Mines, Jeppes town, Park, Doornfontein, and Pretoria. Wanderers, led by Capt. C.L. Winslow (Transvaal Champion), also hosted a local tournament between its own players and those of the United Mines Lawn Tennis Club in September 1894 on its home courts.⁶³ During the same month, the Pretoria Lawn Tennis Club hosted its Ladies Championship tournament which further underlined the dynamic state of activity in the northern colony. Operating conditions, nonetheless, remained challenging. By 1895, for example, the Park Lawn Tennis Club, who had their courts on the Park Square within the perimeters of the central business district, had to share the space for the construction of a telephone exchange. The latter endeavour resulted in the gradual deterioration of the sanitary conditions of the public space due to a distinct lack of regular maintenance, aggravated by the lethargic performance of the Sanitary Board.⁶⁴

59 “Pretoria as It is,” *Cape Times*, July 14, 1881, p. 3.

60 “Lawn Tennis,” *Johannesburg Times*, July 8, 1895, p. 4.

61 “Lawn Tennis,” *Johannesburg Times*, June 19, 1895, p. 4.

62 George A. Parker, *South African Sports* (London: Sampson Low, Marston & Co., 1897), p. 154.

63 “Lawn Tennis,” *Transvaal Argus*, September 14, 1894, p. 3.

64 “To-day,” *Johannesburg Times*, January 17, 1895, p. 2.

By 1896, however, the Wanderers Lawn Tennis Club was struggling to survive, amongst other things as a result of poor management and the loss of capable administrators. With the Wanderers' being the TLTA's leading club, this resulted in the non-hosting of the Transvaal Championship and a general unsettling of the sport in the republic.⁶⁵ This notwithstanding, an Australian visitor during this period observed that the city, in addition to having ice rinks, bicycle tracks, gymnasiums and cricket ovals, also boasted a good number of tennis courts.⁶⁶ Besides private homes, these conveniences were also observed on some mine properties, such as the Simmer & Jack Mines, for the benefit of their white expatriate and local employees.⁶⁷ This ensured the general revival of the sport in the Transvaal, and prominent events like the Wanderers Open Tournament for women and men were reinstated in March 1897.⁶⁸ Shortly thereafter, new clubs—Turffontein, Rosettenville, Johannesburg Presbyterian, Troyeville, and Boksburg—joined the existing group.

In 1884, the Bloemfontein Lawn Tennis Club (BLTC) was established with the objective to organise both formal and informal competitions. Its growth was initially slow and three years later, the club comprised only 50 members. A majority (30) of the paid membership, in accordance with the spirit of the times, were male (Fig. 1). The club, however, boasted a healthy group of 20 female members. Between this date and 1893, the tennis landscape in the city was characterised by at least one public court on Warden Plain in addition to several private courts dispersed throughout the city. A particular highlight for the local club came in 1891, when a local player, Lionel Richardson (Fig. 2), participated in and won the first South African Single's Championship in Port Elizabeth.⁶⁹

By 1891, the South African tennis terrain looked decidedly different with a dense network of tennis clubs and regional associations in operation. The Port Elizabeth Lawn Tennis Club thus saw it fit to launch the inaugural South African Lawn Tennis Open Championships.⁷⁰ This attracted immediate interest across a wide front and, following its first hosting, saw the participation of players based in both rural and urban centres. These included towns such as Port Elizabeth, Grahamstown, Pretoria, Kimberley, East

Figure 2: Lionel Richardson, the first South African male Lawn Tennis Champion (1891).

London, Cape Town, Johannesburg, Fauresmith, Beaufort West, Queenstown, Barkly West, Graaff-Reinet, and Salisbury.⁷¹ Even remote places such as the Umfongosi (correct spelling, Mfongosi) mission community in the very heart of Zululand saw activity:

“Umfongosi Tennis Club came next on the list, and great labour was expended on making proper court. Where you might expect to see men carrying picks or shovels or hammers, tennis balls were more in demand.”⁷²

Lionel Richardson, a Bloemfontein player, became the first SA Men's Single Champion, while Miss Mabel Grant from Natal won the SA Women's Singles Championship in Port Elizabeth.⁷³ The men's doubles title, in turn, was won by Messrs Perry and

65 “Tennis,” *Johannesburg Times*, February 7, 1896, p. 4.

66 “First Impressions of Johannesburg,” *Hobart Mercury*, November 30, 1896, p. 3.

67 “A Great Johannesburg Mine,” *Ballarat Star*, October 7, 1896, p. 4.

68 “Lawn Tennis – Tournament at the Wanderers,” *Johannesburg Times*, March 15, 1897, p. 5.

69 H. Swaffer, *South African Sport* (Johannesburg: Transvaal Leader, 1914), p. 50.

70 “Lawn Tennis Champion Tournament at Port Elizabeth,” *Cape Argus*, April 1, 1891, p. 22.

71 “Lawn Tennis,” *Johannesburg Times*, April 8, 1896, p. 4.

72 “Umfongosi Gold Fields, and Why They are Deserted,” *Cape Argus*, January 21, 1891, p. 12.

73 H. Swaffer, *South African Sport* (Johannesburg: Transvaal Leader, 1914), p. 50.

Grant. Appropriately, the two single championship winners teamed up and also won the inaugural mixed doubles SA Championships that was staged on the occasion.⁷⁴

By March 1893, the men's championship registered 14 entrants, with Richardson the undisputed South African champion following two successive victories. The 'All Comers Ladies Singles' attracted eight entrants and had the national championship and a cup at stake. The tournament further provided for a men's doubles and a mixed-doubles competition. In contrast, the first women's doubles championship was only hosted from 1905 onwards. Similarly, the male competition was accompanied by a handicap system while that of the women had none.⁷⁵ A Ladies Handicap Competition was, however, introduced by the start of the 1895 competition when seven players contested.⁷⁶ By the start of the Anglo-Boer War, participation in the SA Open Tennis Championships was a standard feature of the local tennis programme.

In accordance with the established social practices, participation in the early and championship games and membership of the existing clubs in the 1880-s into the 1890's was restricted to white-only players, since, as the *Cape Argus* suggested, "the races are best socially apart, each good in their own way, but a terribly bad mixture".⁷⁷ Like the case with other European sports, lawn tennis soon attracted a black fanbase, especially amongst educated middle-class blacks who attempted to use the sport to "establish civilized credentials" and to gain acceptance and secure assimilation into white society.⁷⁸ The sport, therefore, became an integral part of the marginalization of blacks and the colonisation process from the onset. In this process, it aided the establishment of a parallel tennis tradition, which continued to be influenced by developments within the dominant practice.

TOWARDS A BLACK TENNIS TRADITION

Over time, lawn tennis, like a range of other sporting codes, also diffused into the wider community and started to attract the interest of all classes, including those individuals who worked as domestic servants.

This was not surprising if one considers the fact that sentenced offenders for example, were often used for the maintenance of the small number of public existing courts.⁷⁹ Furthermore, during 1883, White players in Port Elizabeth staged an exclusive tournament in March – champion racquet given to E.B. Pagden – and in so doing further promoted the attractiveness of the sport.⁸⁰ No similar tournament for interested black players were hosted. During the same year, the editor of the *Christian Express*, a Lovedale newspaper, following a visit to London, recommended lawn tennis for Black women and lasses. It described the sport as "that best of all girls games which is uncommonly like a mild and tame edition of the Red Indian game of lacrosse", and further observed that "surely black girls would not be ruin by lawn tennis", and that "there are worse things than lawn tennis for spoiling Native girls".⁸¹ Similarly, the *Port Elizabeth Telegraph* noted that Miss Waterton (first name unknown) "the lady who has come to South Africa to set us right in the matter of education, advocates lawn tennis for Black girls. Her argument for teaching Kaatje Kekkelbek lawn tennis is that if the church won't amuse Kaatje and her friends, the devil will. Possibly, but even then, there is a missing link in the lady's argument. We can understand the connection of the church with lawn sleeves, but for the life of us we cannot see the connection of the church with lawn tennis".⁸² Such attitude, clearly, discouraged the promotion of lawn tennis amongst black females.

These sentiments notwithstanding, the sport continued to gain broad support among the Black populace:

"*Apa sekuko ne Lawn Tennis!—siqonda njalo. Singa pambili Rini. ... Inga ukudlalwa kwale midlalo yimpi yetu bamnyama yase Rini ibonisa ukuba iyapuma ebunyameni iyasuka ekunyabeni edume ngako neyaziwa ngabo.*" [Now there is also Lawn Tennis!—we understand it that way. We are ahead, Rini. ... Therefore, the playing of these games by our black warriors from Rini shows that it is emerging from darkness, departing from the backwardness for which it is famous and by which it is known.]⁸³

74 Ron Aldridge, "Lawn Tennis," in A. Donaldson (ed.), *The South African Sporting Encyclopaedia and Who's Who* (Johannesburg: Donaldson Publications, 1949), p. 108.

75 "Sport and Amusements," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, March 30, 1893, p. 7.

76 "Lawn Tennis," *Eastern Province Herald*, April 15, 1895, p. 4.

77 Quoted in Vivian Bickford-Smith, *Ethnic Pride and Racial Prejudice in Victorian Cape Town: Group Identity and Social Practice, 1875-1902* (Cape Town: Cambridge, 1995), p. 149.

78 Sundiata A. Djata, *Blacks at the Net: Black Achievement in the History of Tennis*. Vol. 2. (Syracuse Univ. Press, 2006), pp. 52-3.

79 "Weekly Notes," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, September 5, 1882, p. 3.

80 "Local and General News," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, March 22, 1883, p. 2.

81 "The Social Improvement of Christian Natives in Their Homes, Habits etc.," *Christian Express*, August 1, 1883, p. 10.

82 "Weekly Notes," *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, July 24, 1883, p. 5.

83 *Isigidimi Sama-Xosa*, 14, no. 173, May 1, 1884, p. 2. <https://ibali.uct.ac.za/s/isixit/item/15447>. Translated by Thembeke Nxele.

Figure 3: Heidedal Lawn Tennis Club Bloemfontein with mixed gender membership.

By the end of 1883, the *Cape Mercantile Advertiser*, reported the existence of the Native Lawn Tennis Club in Natal. No detail about the club leadership, membership and competition were, however, given.⁸⁴ By 1886, the *Christian Express* reported that a church exhibition from the Girls Industrial Department at Lovedale College, listed among other things, tennis nets manufactured at the school.⁸⁵ Although subsequent accounts indicated that organised playing of the sport were frequently weather dependent, it continued to grow and root itself.⁸⁶ By 1892, W.J.B. Moir, Acting Principal of Lovedale noted in the institution's annual report that "the cricket and tennis club continue to prosper".⁸⁷ This situation remained right up to the start of the Anglo-Boer War. Thus, by the end of the 1880s, the *Australian Town and Country Journal*, related the tale of a Cape female servant (called a 'Kaatje') who upon enquiry, complained that housework or domestic service was too hard and overtly strenuous and that it *interfered with her ability to play tennis* (present author's emphasis). This, noted the correspondent, seemed to

suggest, that "Kaatje and her countrywomen think themselves in many respects quite as good as "them white thrash" at the Cape".⁸⁸

At the start of the 1890s, local black newspapers such as *Imvo Zabantsundu* started to carry advertisements for a range of sports equipment from suppliers such as Dyer & Dyers Co. in King William's Town (currently Qonce). Its April 1890 edition further reported the existence of the Never Give In Lawn Tennis Club (NGILTC) in the north-eastern town or village of Burgersdorp.⁸⁹ A year after the establishment of the NGILTC, *Imvo Zabantsundu* reported the playing of tennis challenge matches between players in Port Elizabeth and Grahamstown (currently Makhanda).⁹⁰ Over the subsequent period the Grahamstown club was joined by the Progress Lawn Tennis Club with a leadership consisting of a Ms A.F. Class, Ms E. Kuze and P. Lemeke.⁹¹ In addition, these clubs were in collaboration or had tennis sections and provided members to each other in case of shortages, or players would have dual membership.⁹² Further additions on the Eastern Cape tennis scene during the

84 "Country News," *Cape Mercantile Advertiser*, December 11, 1883, p. 3.

85 "Girls' Industrial Department – Miss Barnley," *Christian Express*, January 1, 1886, p. 12.

86 "Games and Sports," *Lovedale News*, June 12, 1895, p. 3.

87 "Lovedale Missionary Institution - Other Agencies," *Christian Express*, January 1, 1892, p. 19.

88 "Kaffir 'Slaveys'," *Australian Town and Country Journal* (Sydney, NSW), January 12, 1889, p. 34.

89 "Ibala Labadlali," *Imvo Zabantsundu*, April 3, 1890, p. 2.

90 "I Lawn Tennis," *Imvo Zabantsundu*, March 5, 1890, p. 3.

91 "Ibala Lomdlalo," *Izwi Labantu*, December 24, 1901, p. 3.

92 "Umhla we Kresmes," *Imvo Zabantsundu*, February 11, 1892, p. 3.

Figure 4: Bloemfontein African female Tennis players dressed in contemporary Tennis attire.

Figure 5: Rahab Kgomo – Bloemfontein Tennis player with trophies.

same period, included the founding and activities of the Grahamstown Lawn Tennis Club under the leadership of T.C. Mvula (president), A. Kulati (secretary) and M. Mali (treasurer).⁹³ Parallel to that, news reports noted the activities of the Snowdrop Lawn Tennis Club in Kimberley in the Green Point Location.⁹⁴ They were followed by three more clubs namely Blue Flag, Champion and Some Again – all with a mixed-gender membership.⁹⁵

This same period also saw reports of tennis activity among the black residents of Bloemfontein. This was aided by the availability of equipment and literature, including about and for tennis, which was sold at the Orange Free State Sport Emporium or Barlow Brothers in the city.⁹⁶ The first reported black club shortly after the founding of the Bloemfontein Lawn

Tennis Club (1892) in the white community, was an unknown club established by Duncan Makohliso, an Eastern Cape personality employed on the construction of the railway construction project.⁹⁷ Eight years later the Oriental Lawn Tennis club was established in the segregated area of Waaihoek.⁹⁸ It boasted a mixed membership of males and females of around 30. Soon after its founding, the club called on the City Council to provide courts for the black community, suggesting in its motivation that “it will tend to make us more united with our white brethren”.⁹⁹ This request was, however, not universally welcomed. Contemporary

93 “Ibala Labadlali”, *Imvo Zabantsundu*, February 25, 1892, p. 3.

94 “Indaba – Kimberley”, *Imvo Zabantsundu*, June 16, 1892, p. 2.

95 André Odendaal, *The Story of an African Game* (Johannesburg: New Africa Books, 2003), p. 61.

96 Marianna Botes, “Bloemfontein gedurende die bewind van president F.W. Reitz, 1889-1895: ‘n Kultuurhistoriese studie” (PhD diss. (Cultural History), Free State University, Bloemfontein, 2014), p. 487.

97 André Odendaal, *The Story of an African Game* (Johannesburg: New Africa Books, 2003), p. 59.

98 For a short history of Waaihoek see Karel Schoeman, *Bloemfontein: Die Ontstaan van ‘n Stad, 1846–1946* (Cape Town: Human & Rousseau, 1980).

99 Marianna Botes, “Bloemfontein gedurende die bewind van president F.W. Reitz, 1889-1895: ‘n Kultuurhistoriese studie” (PhD diss. (Cultural History), Free State University, Bloemfontein, 2014), p. 499.

newspapers such as the *Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*, described the general attitude of the Bloemfontein City Council towards Blacks as negative, intolerant, reluctant, disinterested, and characterized by racial superiority. Access to public amenities such as early bioscopes which visited the Colony by 1896 was consequently severely restricted.¹⁰⁰ Further, other organised sports at best were played under primitive conditions.¹⁰¹ In addition to blaming budgetary constraints, some of the serving members of the City Council and their constituency, viewed the provision of public amenities such as the building of a roller-skating rink in Waaihoek, as a potential “underminer of Black morality”.¹⁰²

Despite these problems, lawn tennis continued to find a foothold within black Bloemfontein, amongst both sexes (Fig. 3) but especially among females. Due to the prolific growth of the sport among black women a white reader of the *Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette* complained to the newspaper that “afternoon tea” and tennis and other sport such as hockey were becoming regular institutions and that it was causing a domestic labour shortage within the city.¹⁰³ Against this background, others such as the Afrikaner Bond in the Cape Colony, based on a public speech by a Mr T.P. Theron, a Member of the Legislative Assembly for Vryburg and the Afrikaner Bond, in November 1895, objected to spending tax-payers money on government-aided schools for blacks. He was also of the opinion that Blacks should be taught to work and further objected to the phenomenon of black girls playing lawn tennis (Figs 4 & 5) (“the Bond did not want such things as that”) as reported by some newspapers.¹⁰⁴ This

notwithstanding, black interest in lawn tennis continue to grow. Clubs also emerged in Johannesburg and Krugersdorp, including one named the Champion Lawn Tennis Club who often participated in Christmas tournaments together with their cricket counterparts. Due to a lack of newspaper coverage and the absence of public archives, reconstructing its influence is impossible at this stage.

CONCLUSION

By the start of the Second Anglo-Boer War (South African War) in 1899, South Africa indeed had established a meaningful and growing tennis tradition. In accordance with the spirit of the times and the prevailing custom of social segregation of society tennis developed as two parallel streams – a white, or European, versus a Black tradition. During this process, a range of individuals, groups and institutions made a critical contribution to its establishment and growth. Within this group were a significant number of retailers and other businessmen, government officials, soldiers, mission schools and the mines. Given their divergent interests, their involvement left a distinct imprint on the nature and features of the South African game. Where the main adherents came from the middle classes, lawn tennis clubs served as institutions and markers of social distinction and meeting places for the political influential and for those who had achieved prominence in society. For mission schools with their civilization mission, the sport was utilized to inculcate certain desirable principles, including sportsmanship, teamwork, constructive leisure, etc.

100 Johannes Haasbroek, “Die ontstaan van die eerste bioskoop (1922) vir die swart gemeenskap van Bloemfontein,” *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum Bloemfontein*, 17, no. 6 (2001): 140 (138-160). https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA00679208_2769

101 Johannes Haasbroek, “Die sosiale en vermaaklikheidslewe van die swart inwoners van Waaihoek, Bloemfontein, tydens die Oranjerivierkolonie-tydperk (1900-1910),” *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum Bloemfontein*, 13, no. 4 (1997): 149 (137-68). https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA00679208_1028

102 Johannes Haasbroek, “Die verhouding tussen die swart inwoners en die Stadsraad van Bloemfontein gedurende die Oranjerivierkolonie-tydperk, 1902-1910,” *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum Bloemfontein*, 15, no. 1 (1999): 5-8 (1-28). https://hdl.handle.net/10520/AJA00679208_1966

103 Karel Schoeman, *Bloemfontein: Die ontstaan van 'n stad, 1846–1946* (Cape Town: Human & Rousseau, 1980), p. 220.

104 “Politics at Vryburg,” *Cape Times*, November 20, 1895, p. 7.